

THE THEORETICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF DEVELOPING MUSICAL CULTURE IN PRIMARY CLASS PUPILS

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Abstract. *The given article presents the pedagogical and psychological possibilities for improving the methodology of developing musical culture in primary school pupils. It also highlights the views of our scholars and the significance of their sources in the field of musical art.*

Keywords: *music, culture, creativity, pupil, memory, psychologist, art, classics, pedagogy, melody, song, dance, ability.*

It is important to suggest that the mindset, lifestyle and spiritual outlook of any nation or people do not form on their own. Their emergence and development are based on specific historical, natural and social factors a fact well understood by all of us. The spiritual values, culture, history, and uniqueness of a people along with their restoration, play a decisive and essential role in renewing and advancing our society, and this is recognized by the global community.

In considering human development, it is crucial to reflect deeply on the influence and importance of the world of spirituality. In the complex era of present time, when our people are building the foundations of a new life and society, defining the tasks related to nurturing a spiritually healthy and well-rounded generation has become a vital necessity. Every individual living in this land, especially the younger generation, must first become aware of their identity, gain a deeper understanding of our ancient history, rich culture, and the legacy of our great ancestors, and develop the ability to think independently and consciously engage with the rapidly changing realities of modern life. Achieving this noble goal is impossible without the art of music.

At present time there is a strong social and pedagogical need to organize musical culture based on innovative pedagogical technologies and to enhance the effectiveness of pupils' musical culture-one of the main activities of the "Musical Culture" subject taught in general secondary schools. Therefore, in recent years, the issue of effectively utilizing the potential of our national culture and art as an important educational tool has become increasingly relevant.

According to psychologists, a person can't be born with all abilities, but rather with certain capacities that serve as a source for the development and realization of abilities. Ability is an individual characteristic of a person that serves as a subjective condition for successfully performing a certain type of activity. Every ability manifests itself during the process of activity. Potential does not develop on its own as it requires a favorable environment for its development. Sometimes, a child may be born with a natural inclination for music, but if a supportive environment is not provided for the development of their musical traits, this potential may remain undeveloped. One of the leading factors in the formation of a person as an individual is the environment. By environment, we mean the totality of external events that influence a person,

which can be further divided into natural, social, family, and other types of environments.

It is worth mentioning that Aristotle expressed the following view regarding the musical modes that influence the psyche: “Music in one mode can make a person gentle and compassionate, while another can lead to excitement and nervousness.”

According to him, melodies in the Phrygian, Dorian, and Lydian modes have a positive effect on a person’s health and spirit. He recommended that music in other modes should not be introduced to the ears of the younger generation.

Without first developing a sense of beauty in a person, it is impossible to speak of a spiritually mature individual. Music is one of the most powerful tools for shaping and nurturing such delicate emotions. Only those whose hearts are attuned to beauty can truly love and understand music. Listening to music and perceiving it is something that is cultivated and instilled from childhood.

As the great writer Chingiz Aitmatov once said, “Only music can overcome the false ideologies of eras and constantly strive toward the future.” [2]

Abu Nasr al-Farabi, Ibn Sina (Avicenna), al-Khwarizmi, and their successors created scientific works on music theory (known as *Ilm al-Musika*). Scholars of the East opened up an entire era in the history of the development of the science of music. In this regard, Farabi described music by saying, “Healing the soul through the influence of beautiful sounds is beneficial for health.”

The universally recognized encyclopedic scholar and founder of medical science, Abu Ali Ibn Sina, emphasized: “Two things are necessary for the development of an infant’s body: one is gently rocking the baby, the other is the mother’s song (lullaby). The first affects the body, and the second affects the soul.” [3]

In improving the methodology of developing musical culture among primary school pupils, the insights and sources of our great scholars are of significant importance. Every melody, song, dance, and musical piece taught should glorify our homeland, awaken positive qualities in individuals, inspire goodness and promote values such as friendship and bravery.

Unfortunately, nowadays, “entertainment songs”, which may have pleasant melodies but are shallow in meaning, irrelevant to youth, neither harmful nor beneficial, and do not promote virtue have become widespread, negatively influencing people’s consciousness. Melody and song are essential spiritual and emotional elements for individuals to develop and live as social beings.

One of the disciplines that promotes such meaningful music is the subject of Musical Culture. This subject represents one of the most widespread forms of human artistic expression. It actively engages nearly all segments of society in artistic and cultural activities and fosters unity. Music cultivates in the younger generation an interest in the legacy of folk music, national heritage, and the masterpieces of European classical music. It encourages harmony and solidarity, while also helping to overcome various physiological and psychological issues such as stuttering, difficulty expressing thoughts, weak memory, shyness, excessive sensitivity, irritability and distractibility.

Definitely, these particular qualities of music serve as core factors in shaping pupils’ musical culture. Historically, scholars and philosophers from both the East and the West have sought to master musical instruments and vocal performance. They believed that harmonizing the heartbeat with music helps to focus thoughts, organize the mind, heal the body, and find solutions to problems. Therefore, music can be a powerful tool for both the spiritual and physiological

education and development of individuals. [4]

The famous Polish composer Karol Szymanowski, speaking about the natural power of music, emphasized that it can be used in two opposing directions creation and destruction. He stated, “Just as the waters of a fast-flowing river, when properly channeled, can be used for productive and useful purposes, such as turning a mill, the power of music should likewise be utilized effectively.” It is also appropriate to recall the words of A.P. Asafyev: “Music is both art, science, language and play.”

The emotions expressed through music are often very difficult to convey with words. It is no coincidence that the saying goes, “Where words fail, music speaks.” Music has a strong emotional impact on pupils as it brings them joy and evokes positive feelings. When pupils are exposed to meaningful, engaging, and enjoyable music, it puts them in a good mood.

One of the most pressing and important issues of today is the extent to which our rare national melodies, songs, and dances, passed down through generations, are being instilled in the minds and spirits of primary school pupils. It is crucial to preserve and protect these traditions, ensuring that they are understood and appreciated with a fresh perspective, and actively enriched for future generations. The process of embedding these values into the consciousness of the younger generation through the subject of musical literacy should be seen as a critical task.

Pedagogues, who are the backbone of society, can only earn the status of mentors capable of leading young people toward spiritual maturity by wholeheartedly dedicating themselves to their profession and responding to the demands of the time.

However, the role of music, especially its culture, in the formation of a well-rounded individual is unparalleled compared to other important fields such as science, literature, and visual arts. The Uzbek people, since ancient times, have possessed a rich musical heritage, along with moral and cultural values that have evolved over the centuries. This heritage includes musical treatises, manuscripts created by our great scholars, the musical instruments they crafted, songs, melodies, dances, as well as the traditions of master-apprentice relationships. These elements have been polished and celebrated through various festivals, gatherings, and musical events that continue to be honored and reflected upon today.

Definitely, music enters our imagination in the form of various images, deeply affecting the human spirit, uplifting the heart and mind. Only those who enjoy pleasant music can appreciate its melody, nourishing their soul and enriching their imagination. In moments of personal problems or feelings of helplessness, stepping away from them by listening to soothing music or dancing to an enchanting song helps one feel more grounded, and through these contrasting situations, individuals begin to find the strength to act boldly.

Surprisingly, our ancestors have left us a rich cultural heritage, and over the centuries, diverse songs and melodies have been created based on the lifestyles, living conditions, and climates of different regions of our republic. Musical instruments were also crafted. Studying these, applying them to life, and passing them on to future generations are important tasks that lie ahead of us.

Certainly, music by creating images in the listener's imagination, deeply resonates with the human spirit, and pleasant, harmonious music evokes a sense of well-being, bringing upliftment to the soul. A person inspired by pleasant music gains confidence in their own strength, drawing nourishment from it. When faced with certain problems or helplessness in life, one feels grounded and becomes ready to demonstrate courage in various situations.

It is known that playing on untuned musical instruments, singing off-key or performing works with overly trivial and shallow content can disrupt the listener's mood. Under the influence of such music, the listener may start to feel nervous and may even declare open opposition to such music, attempting to remove it. When it is impossible to stop such distorted renditions, nervous tension in the listener may arise. In music, uplifting moods not only express joy and happiness but can also lead to the emergence of certain characteristics from the heroes of the musical piece in the listeners.

At the same time, tragic situations are also expressed in musical works. The readiness to sacrifice oneself for love, the pain of unfulfilled desires and dreams, and similar tragic conditions are clearly manifested in various genres of music. Humorous characters and satires that bring laughter to the listener also find their expression in our musical works.

However, the methodology for developing musical culture in primary school pupils is a fundamental aspect of the educational process. It serves to introduce pupils and youth to classical music heritage, promoting the activities of amateur clubs and folk musical instrument groups organized in cultural centers and art galleries. This contributes to the further development of music as an art form. In these clubs, it is important to popularize our national values, traditions, and the art and culture of fraternal nations. Through this, we foster and shape feelings of patriotism and internationalism in the youth.

By summarizing it should be suggested that based on the above interpretation, we can conclude that music, in whatever form or manifestation, becomes a powerful tool for spiritual, emotional, and artistic-aesthetic education due to its influence. Music, being one of humanity's greatest discoveries, is an endless treasure.

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